

STUDIES OF SOME PHYSICAL FACTORS IN THE ELECTRO-DEPOSITION OF NICKEL ON IRON.

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Results are given for the optimum conditions for the production of a smooth, bright and adherent deposit of nickel on iron from a bath containing nickel sulphate, nickel chloride and boric acid. Data are given for the cathode efficiency in respect of nickel deposition under the influence of the electrolyte concentration, the current density, the duration, the inter-electrode distance, the temperature, the agitation of the bath, the superposition of A.C., and that of the addition of a large number of organic and inorganic agents in different proportions, such as aluminium sulphate, chromic acid, cadmium chloride, hydrogen peroxide, gelatine etc. The possible role of the addition agents is also discussed.

Detailed measurements are made of the cathode efficiency of nickel in the presence of methyl and ethyl alcohol, glycerol, mannitol and sucrose whose proportions were varied over a wide range. Data are also given for conductivity, relative viscosity and density.

Introduction by Adams in 1866 of aqueous nickel ammonium sulphate for the nickel bath was soon followed by important advances in the technique of the metal deposition and the diversity of its applications. The value of the nickel coat is chiefly due to (i) the brilliant lustre on polishing, (ii) its durability in contact with the atmosphere, suffering little tarnishing, and (iii) hardness and mechanical strength. The use of the above bath material had, however, suffered from considerable drawback, as thick and coherent deposits could not be procured. This was attributed to the use of ammonia by Madsen (*Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1921, 39, 483). This view was confirmed by Foerster (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1897, 4, 160). Thick lustrous and adherent deposits of nickel were obtained by using (a) nickel sulphate or nickel chloride (*cf.* Foerster, *loc. cit.*; Karl Engemann, *ibid.*, 1911, 17, 910), (b) a single salt of nickel (*cf.* Merrick, *Chem. News*, 1910, 26, 209) and (c) a single salt of nickel in the presence of an ammonium salt (*cf.* Fischer, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1907, 13, 361). Very satisfactory results were also obtained from a solution containing nickel ammonium sulphate and a conducting salt like ammonium chloride or nickel chloride (*cf.* Kasyer, *Chem. Zentil.*, 1878, 127; Bennet, Kenny and Dugliss, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1914, 18, 373). Riedel (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1915, 21, 5; 1916, 22, 281) studied the electrodeposition of nickel from the chloride solution containing free HCl and CH₃COOH. Kohlschuter and Vuilleumier (*ibid.*, 1918, 24, 300)

made an extensive study of the deposition of nickel from various solutions under differing conditions. Bath consisting of nickel sulphate, nickel chloride and boric acid was first suggested by Hammond (*Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1916, 30, 103); it was used with some modification by later workers (cf. Watts, *ibid.*, 1931, 59, 193; *Month. Rev. Amer. Electroplater's Soc.*, 1931, No. 3, 4; Phillips, *Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1930, 58, 221; 1931, 59, 393; Phillips and co-workers, *ibid.*, 1930, 58, 207, 241; Stager, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1920, 3, 584; Potter, *E.P.*, 244, 166; Gardner *U.S.P.*, 1642, 235; Eckardt, *Chem. Zentr.*, 1934, II, 3040; Arnold and co-workers, *B.P.*, 437224; Roub, *Mitt. Forsch. Inst., Edelmit Schwal Grund*, 1935) and others studied the influence of adding foreign substances as addition agents. Phillips (*Month. Rev. Amer. Electroplater's Soc.*, 1932, 19, No. 2, 9) and Cuthbertson (*Metallurgia*, 1932, 7, 557) concluded that addition of organic substances were of no use in a nickel bath. Isgarischev and Ravikovitch (*J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 62, 255) investigated the influence of adding a large number of inorganic salts, especially the chlorides of alkali and alkaline earth metals, to the plating bath. With the exception of the work by Harr (*Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1933; 64, 203), Essin and Alfimova (*ibid.*, 1935, 68, 255) and of Fedoteev and Kinkulski (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1935, 224, 337) but little quantitative data are available in the literature on nickel deposition under differing conditions. In the present investigation an attempt has, therefore, been made to obtain this information quantitatively in respect of the influence of several factors (*vide infra*).

EXPERIMENTAL.

The electrolysis was carried out in a small glass trough of about 200 c.c. capacity, kept immersed in a thermostat and maintained at the desired temperature. The temperature of the bath solution was controlled within $\pm 0.2^\circ$. The anode used was a thick plate of nickel (99-99.9%) of size 3.5×3 cm. A thin plate (3×3 cm. approx.) of iron serving as the cathode was first rendered free from grease by dipping it in a hot alkaline solution (43 g. Na_2CO_3 , 17 g. NaOH and 13 g. Na_3PO_4 in 1000 c.c. water) for a few minutes and then washing it with water; it was next immersed in moderately strong nitric acid to remove surface scales and rust and to loosen the coating of carbon. It was then well washed with water and was made an anode in the etching solution (100 g. H_2SO_4 and 100 g. Na_2SO_4 in 1000 c.c. water) and current was passed for 15-20 minutes. The plate was made an anode to prevent it from becoming brittle owing to the occlusion

of hydrogen evolved at the cathode. This gave an uniformly etched and smooth surface. It was next rubbed with sodium carbonate and washed with water. It was, afterwards, dipped momentarily into the 'bright dip' (5 parts by weight of 55Be-H₂SO₄ and 1 part concentrated HNO₃; 1000 c.c. of this solution containing 1.57 g. of NaCl), which imparted an additional brightness to the plate. The plate was then washed with distilled water and finally with alcohol, dried and weighed accurately. A copper coulometer was used to give the measure of the quantity of electricity passed through the electrolyte; the coulometer solution was prepared according to Otte's recommendations (*Chem. Ztg.*, 1893, 17, 543). The current was obtained from storage cells; the circuit included an electrolytic bath, copper coulometer, a precision type ammeter and an adjustable resistance in series and voltmeter, connected across the electrodes in the bath.

Two stock solutions (A) and (B) were prepared; (A) was made by dissolving 280.7 g. of pure crystallised NiSO₄ · 7H₂O in 1000 c.c. water and (B) by dissolving 25 g. of NiCl₂ · 6H₂O and 50 g. of boric acid in 1000 c.c. water. The solutions used in the following experiments were prepared by mixing (A) and (B) in the required proportion or with the appropriate dilution or additions of the other materials used in this work. The strength of the mixed solutions, containing the same amounts, *viz.*, 12.5 and 25 g. of NiCl₂ · 6H₂O and H₃BO₃ respectively, per litre of the solution, is expressed, for the sake of convenience, in terms of mols per litre, of NiSO₄ · 7H₂O only (Tables IA & II). The p_H values given for the solutions used in this work are colorimetric, uncorrected. The precaution, to switch on the current before the plate (cathode) was introduced, was always observed to avoid the deposition of nickel by immersion. To investigate the optimum conditions for the production of smooth lustrous and adherent deposit of nickel the following factors were studied, over ranges as indicated:

	Optimum conditions	
(a) Electrolyte concentration, <i>M</i> to <i>M</i> /4	...	∴ <i>M</i> /2
(b) Current density, 5 to 108 amp./sq. ft.	...	∴ 15 amp./sq. ft.
(c) Time, 5 to 60 minutes	...	∴ 30 min.
(d) Inter-electrode distance, 5 to 2 cm.	...	∴ 3.5 cm.

Measurements were made of the cathode efficiency for Ni-deposition in respect of the influence of the factors (a), (b) (Tables II and III), temperature (Table IVA, B, c), agitation of the bath and superimposition of A.C. (Table V), cathode material (Table VI), addition of (i) organic and inorganic agents (Table VII) in small quantities, *viz.*, HgCl₂, CdCl₂, SnCl₂,

$Al_2(SO_4)_3$, $18H_2O$, CrO_3 , glue, thymol, egg-albumin, dextrine, H_2O_2 , pyridine, CS_2 and acetone and of (ii) non-electrolytes (Tables VIII to XII) in larger proportions, *viz.*, methyl and ethyl alcohol, glycerol, mannitol and sucrose. The nature of the nickel deposit produced in each of these experiments is also recorded as examined with a microscope. The cathode efficiency in any given experiment was calculated by the relation,

$$\% \text{ Cathode efficiency} = \frac{100 \times \text{equiv. wt. of Cu} \times \text{wt. of Ni deposit}}{\text{Equiv. wt. of Ni} \times \text{wt. of Cu (coulometer) deposit}}$$

To obtain further information in regard to the results obtained for the influence of methyl and ethyl alcohol, glycerol, mannitol and sucrose on the depositional behaviour of the bath solution, corresponding electrolytic conductivity was determined on a Pye's modified Post Office Box with the usual precautions (*cf.* Joshi and Solanki, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **14**, 323; 1940, **17**, 627). The cell constant determined by using $N/50$ -KCl was found to be 0.3777. These results are given in column 6 of Tables VIII to XII. Relative viscosity was determined for each of the above mixtures by using Ostwald's and Scarpa's (in few cases) method at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ with the usual precautions (*cf.* Joshi and Solanki, *loc. cit.*). Specific gravities corresponding to these were determined at the above temperature. These results are given in columns 7 and 8 in Tables VIII to XII.

Results showing the influence on cathode efficiency of electrolyte concentration, current density and temperature are shown graphically in Fig. 1. Similarly the cathode efficiency, specific conductivity, relative viscosity and specific gravity are plotted against percentages of the non-electrolyte added by appropriate selection of the scale units in the same figure to economise space, in Figs. 2 and 3.

TABLE IA.

Variation of electrolyte concentration.

Temp. = 30° . $p_H = 5.2 - 6.0$. Time = 30 min. Inter-electrode distance = 5 cm. C.D. = 18 amp./sq. ft.

Electrolyte conc.	Nature of deposit.
M	Good, bright and uniform deposit with fine structure.
M/2	Very good, bright and improved deposit with fine-grained structure.
M/4	Fairly bright deposit with uniform structure.

TABLE IB.

*Variation of the duration of electrolysis.*Conc. = $M/2$. C.D. = 8 amp./sq. ft. Other factors same as in Table IA.

Time.	Nature of deposit.
5 min.	Very thin and dull deposit.
10	Do.
15	Improvement in the deposit.
30	Fairly good and bright deposit with fine structure.
60	Do.
120	Do.

TABLE IC.

*Variation of current density.*Conc. = $M/2$. Other factors same as in Table IA.

C.D. in amp./sq. ft.	Nature of deposit.
5'0	Practically no deposition of the metal; evolution of hydrogen at the cathode.
8'0	Fairly good and bright deposit with fine-grained structure.
15'0	Bright, lustrous and shining deposit.
20'0	Very bright and uniform deposit; improvement in the structure.
30'0	Do.
37'0	Do.
45'0	Lustre of the deposit gets diminished.
59'0	Dull and greyish black deposit showing a tendency to 'peel' off.
77'8	The deposit especially at the edges is loose, powdery and black, and gets easily washed off.
108'6	Burnt and powdery deposit all over the plate; rapid evolution of hydrogen.

TABLE ID.

*Variation of inter-electrode distance.*Conc. = $M/2$. Temp. = 30°. Time = 30 min. $p_H = 5'2-6'0$.
C.D. = 30 amp./sq. ft.

Inter-electrode distance.	Nature of deposit.
5	Fairly good and uniform deposit.
3'5	Bright and lustrous deposit with fine-grained structure
2'0	Do.

TABLE II.

Effect of concentration.

Inter-electrode distance = 3.5 cm. Time = 30-40 min.

Temp. = 25°. $p_2 = 5.6$. C.D. = 12.5 amp./sq. ft.

Conc.	Ni deposit.	Cu deposit (Coulometer).	Cathode efficiency.	Conc.	Ni deposit.	Cu deposit (Coulometer).	Cathode efficiency.
M	0.0328 g.	0.0578 g.	61.4	M/8	0.0295	0.0621	51.4
	0.0340	0.0604	61.0		0.0318	0.0665	51.8
M/2	0.0444	0.0828	58.1	M/16	0.0335	0.0748	48.5
	0.0446	0.0823	58.7		0.0336	0.0751	48.5
M/4	0.0304	0.0606	54.4				
	0.0385	0.0766	54.5				

TABLE III.

*Effect of current density.*Conc. = M/2. $p_2 = 5.6$. Temp. = 25°. Inter-electrode distance = 3.5 cm.

C.D. (amp./sq. ft.)	Ni deposit.	Cu deposit. (Coulometer).	Cathode efficiency.	C.D. (amp./sq. ft.)	Ni deposit.	Cu deposit. (Coulometer)	Cathode efficiency.
2.5	0.0000 g.	0.0584 g.	0.0	20.0	0.0807	0.0962	90.8
					0.0807	0.0963	90.7
6.5	0.0181	0.0562	36.4	25.0	0.1153	0.1289	96.8
	0.0199	0.0590	36.5		0.1094	0.1203	96.8
	0.0272	0.0636	46.4	27.5	0.1320	0.1504	94.9
9.4	0.0277	0.0643	46.9		0.1062	0.1206	95.0
	0.0572	0.0936	66.1	37.5	0.1577	0.2346	72.3
13.0	0.0571	0.0936	66.0		0.1267	0.1916	72.1

TABLE IV.A.

*Influence of temperature.*Conc. = M/2. $p_2 = 5.6$. Time = 20-30 min. Inter-electrode distance

= 3.5 cm. C.D. = 8 amp./sq. ft.

Temp.	Ni deposit.	Cu deposit.	Cathode efficiency.	Remarks.
15°	0.0121 g.	0.0422 g.	31.1%	Bright deposit with granular structure.
25	0.0229	0.0603	41.6	Bright and coarse deposit.
35	0.0232	0.0471	52.3	Bright, smooth and uniform deposit.
50	0.0256	0.0478	58.0	Much improvement in the structure.
70	0.0263	0.0484	58.7	Deposit gets blackened or burnt.
85	0.0283	0.0518	59.2	Loose, powdery and black deposit.

TABLE IVB.

Influence of temperature.

C.D. = 15 amp./sq. ft. Other factors same as in Table IVA.

Temp	Ni deposit.	Cu deposit	Cathode efficiency.	Remarks.
15°	0.0504 g.	0.0918 g.	59.5%	Bright but coarse deposit.
25	0.0572	0.0936	66.1	Do.
35	0.0638	0.0921	75.0	Much improvement in the structure.
50	0.0710	0.0932	82.5	Very bright and smooth deposit.
70	0.0608	0.0748	88.0	Deposit blackens and shows a tendency to peel off.
85	0.0516	0.0613	91.2	Loose, powdery and burnt deposit.

TABLE IVc.

Influence of temperature.

C.D. = 25 amp./sq. ft. Other factors same as in Table IVA.

Temp.	Ni deposit	Cu deposit.	Cathode efficiency.	Remarks.
15°	0.0785 g.	0.1038 g.	81.9%	Good and satisfactory deposit.
25	0.1094	0.1203	96.8	Very bright and shining deposit with fine-grained structure.
35	0.1346	0.1502	97.0	Do.
50	0.0907	0.0989	97.6	Deposit becomes coarse and nodular.
70	0.1088	0.1238	95.1	Dull, black and coarse deposit
85	0.1026	0.1178	94.5	Do.

TABLE V.

*Effect of agitation and superimposing A.C. on D.C.*Conc. = $M/2$. $p_H = 5.6$. Temp. = 25°. Time = 30 min.

Inter-electrode distance = 3.5 cm.

C.D. in amps./sq. ft.		Cathode efficiency.	Remarks.
15.0	Without agitation.	66.1%	Deposit bright but granular.
	With "	63.4	Better and improved deposit with fine-grained structure.
50.0	Without agitation.	—	Dull and burnt deposit with irregular structure.
	With "	—	Much improvement in the lustre of the deposit; irregularity of the structure gets lessened.
15.0	A.C. superimposed	20.1	A.C. was first started and then followed by D.C.
		20.8	D.C. was first started and then A.C. superimposed.

TABLE VI.

Effect of the cathode material.

C.D. = 15 amp./sq. ft. Other factors same as in Table V.

Cathode material.	Ni deposit.	Cu deposit (Coulometer).	Cathode efficiency.	Remarks.
Iron	0.0572 g.	0.0932 g.	66.1%	Good, shining and granular deposit.
Cu (polished)	0.0776	0.1198	70.2	Fairly good deposit with fine structure.
	0.0709	0.1088	70.4	
Cu (plated)	0.0734	0.1141	69.6	Do.
	0.0780	0.1207	69.8	
Cd (plated)	0.0706	0.1140	68.1	Shining and granular deposit.
	0.0549	0.0872	68.1	
Ni (")	0.0736	0.1206	66.1	Very good deposit with fine structure.
	0.0662	0.1092	66.2	
Co (")	0.0698	0.1120	67.8	Do.
	0.0774	0.1232	68.1	
Hg (Cu-amalgamated)	0.0740	0.1138	70.4	Dull-white deposit.
	0.0744	0.1146	70.3	
Pb	0.0701	0.1076	70.5	Fine, regular and coherent deposit.
	0.0704	0.1080	70.6	
Sn	0.0556	0.0888	67.8	Do.
	0.0555	0.0886	67.8	
Ag (plated)	0.0662	0.1125	65.8	Amorphous deposit with pitting effect.
	0.0698	0.1156	65.8	
Au (plated)	0.0661	0.1093	66.0	Shining, crystalline and fine deposit.
	0.0631	0.1034	66.1	
Cr (plated)	0.0693	0.1090	68.8	Powdery and amorphous deposit
	0.0671	0.1076	68.5	
Pt (smooth)	0.060	0.0984	65.7	Non-coherent deposit with pitting effect.
	0.058	0.0952	65.9	

TABLE VII.

Influence of addition agents.

C.D. = 15 amp./sq. ft. Other factors same as in Table V.

Addition agent	Amount of (A) in 100 c.c. soln.	Ni deposit	Cu deposit (coulometer).	Cathode efficiency.	Remarks.
Nil	0	0.0572 g.	0.0936 g.	66.1%	Bright & granular deposit.
HgCl ₂	0.1 g	...	...	...	Dull & black deposit.
CdCl ₂	0.005	...	...	...	Good & shining deposit.
"	0.013	...	...	...	Do.
"	0.025	0.072	0.1050	69.1	} Much improvement in the deposit.
"	"	0.072	0.1046	69.2	
"	0.05	0.0542	0.0824	71.2	} 71.4 Deposit very bright and lustrous.
"	0.05	0.0570	0.0862	71.6	
"	0.25	0.0547	0.0824	72.1	Deposit gets blackened.
SnCl ₂	0.013	...	...	...	No improvement.
"	0.03	...	...	..	Deposit dull, black and unsatisfactory.
Al ₂ (SO ₄) ₃ , 18H ₂ O	0.1	0.0564	0.0928	66.0	Deposit shining but coarse
"	0.5	0.0445	0.0766	63.0	} 63.0 Much improvement.
"	"	0.0445	0.0766	63.0	
"	1.0	0.0443	0.0744	62.0	Bright, lustrous and fine-grained deposit.
"	2.0	0.0446	0.0782	60.8	Bright but nodular deposit.
CrO ₃	0.005	0.0304	0.1082	30.4	} 30.5 Dull and black deposit with irregular structure.
"	"	0.0306	0.1088	30.7	
"	0.01	0.0210	0.1051	21.6	} 21.7 Do.
"	"	0.0218	0.1084	21.8	
"	0.02	0.0096	0.1306	7.96	} 7.95 Very thin and black deposit.
"	"	0.0096	0.1308	7.94	
"	0.025	0.0000	0.1082	0.0	} 0.0 No deposit; copious evolution of hydrogen.
"	"	0.0000	0.1084	0.0	
H ₂ O ₂ 3%	0.025 c.c.	0.0427	0.0663	60.8	} 69.8 Shining deposit with fine structure.
"	"	0.0429	0.0666	69.8	

TABLE VII (contd.).

Addition agent (A)	Amount of (A) in 100 c.c. soln.	Ni deposit.	Cu deposit (coulometer).	Cathode efficiency.	Remark.
H ₂ O ₂ (3%)	0.05 c.c.	0.0448 g.	0.0666g.	72.9	72.9% Shining deposit with fine structure.
		0.0448	0.0666	72.9	
"	0.10	0.0504	0.0693	78.6	78.6 Further improvement in structure.
		0.0502	0.0690	78.6	
"	0.20	0.050	0.0650	83.3	83.4 Diminution in lustre.
		0.0508	0.0662	83.5	
"	0.50	0.0506	0.064	85.6	Greyish-white deposit.
"	1.0	0.0528	0.0646	88.9	Greyish and black deposit
Pyridine	0.0025	...	...	...	Deposit gets spoiled.
CS ₂	0.0025	...	...	...	Black streaks throughout the plate.
Acetone	0.5	...	...	...	Dull and black deposit
Glee	0.01 g.	0.0384	0.0662	66.7	66.7 Bright and shining deposit with nodular structure
		0.0385	0.0664	66.7	
"	0.05	0.0546	0.0908	66.3	66.3 Do.
		0.0546	0.0908	66.3	
"	0.1	0.0512	0.0781	66.0	66.1 Deposit gets blackened and spoiled.
		0.0520	0.0788	66.1	
Thymol	0.01	0.0568	0.0928	66.1	66.1 No improvement.
		0.0571	0.0932	66.1	
"	0.05	...	...	...	Dull deposit shows a tendency to peel off.
Egg-albumin	0.01 g.	0.0405	0.0664	66.0	66.0 No improvement.
		0.040	0.0656	66.0	
"	0.05	—	—	—	Bad and dull deposit showing a tendency to peel off.
Dextrine	0.005	0.040	0.0648	66.2	Slight improvement in the structure.
"	0.01	0.0401	0.0655	66.2	Bright, lustrous and fine grained deposit.
"	0.05	0.0401	0.0656	66.2	Do.
"	0.10	—	—	—	Fine structure but brightness gets diminished.
Gelatine	0.01	0.0478	0.0814	66.0	Coarse deposit with diminished lustre.
"	0.05	0.0399	0.0648	66.2	Do.
"	0.1	—	—	—	Do.

TABLE VIII.

Influence of methyl alcohol

Bath = *Mjz* (after mixing). Temp. = 25°. C.D. = 15 amp./sq. ft. $p_n = 5.6$.
Inter-electrode distance = 3.5 cm.

Amount of MeOH in 100 c.c.	Ni deposit	Cu deposit (coulometer).	Cathode efficiency.	Remarks.	Sp. condy. (mhos).	Relative viscosity.	Relative density.
0.0 c.c.	0.0572 g.	0.0932 g.	66.08 %	Bright & coarse deposit.	0.0348	1.344	1.101
1.0	0.0468	0.0736	68.9	} 65.9 Do.	0.03411	1.370	1.098
	0.0467	0.0736	68.8				
2.0	0.0470	0.0724	70.1	} 70.1 Bright and fine grained deposit.	0.03271	1.398	1.096
	0.0472	0.0728	70.0				
5.0	0.043	0.0658	70.7	} 70.7 Do.	0.02895	1.613	1.094
	0.0431	0.0660	70.8				
10.0	0.0431	0.0664	70.5	} 70.5 Less shining deposit.	0.02561	1.750	1.088
	0.0431	0.0664	70.5				
20.0	0.0438	0.0676	70.09	} 70.1 Greyish white deposit	0.02223	1.882	1.074
	0.044	0.068	70.11				

TABLE IX.

Influence of ethyl alcohol.

Conditions same as in Table VIII.

Amount of EtOH in 100 c.c. soln.	Ni deposit	Cu deposit (coulometer).	Cathode efficiency.	Remarks.	Sp. Condy. (mhos).	Relative viscosity.	Relative density.
0.0 c.c.	0.0572 g.	0.0932 g.	66.06 %	Bright & coarse deposit.	0.0348	1.344	1.101
0.5	0.0508	0.081	67.9	} 67.8 Do.	0.0342	1.372	1.100
	0.0532	0.085	67.8				
1.0	0.046	0.0724	69.0	} 68.9 Improvement in the structure.	0.0336	1.402	1.098
	0.0462	0.0722	68.8				
2.0	0.0544	0.0843	70.02	} 70.0 Do.	0.0323	1.451	1.096
	0.0552	0.0855	70.04				
5.0	0.0493	0.0756	70.76	} 70.8 Structure very fine.	0.0285	1.570	1.093
	0.0492	0.0764	70.80				
10.0	0.0497	0.0766	70.6	} 70.6 Do.	0.02327	1.801	1.087
	0.0498	0.0766	70.7				

TABLE X
Influence of glycerin.

Conditions same as in Table VIII.

Amount of glycerin in 100 c.c. soln.	Ni deposit.	Cu deposit (conglomerate).	Cathode efficiency.	Remarks.	Sp. condy. (mhos).	Relative viscosity.	Relative density.
0.0 c.c.	0.0572 g.	0.0932 g.	66.08%	Bright & coarse deposit.	0.0348	1.344	1.101
1.0	0.0480	0.0776	67.0	67.1 Do.	0.0335	1.408	1.104
	0.0499	0.0803	67.2				
2.5	0.0492	0.0775	68.7	68.6 Do.	0.0313	1.510	1.108
	0.0432	0.0684	68.5				
5.0	0.0449	0.0706	68.9	68.9 Brightness gets diminished.	0.02504	1.683	1.115
	0.0451	0.0708	68.9				
10.0	0.0424	0.0666	68.95	68.9 Grey-white deposit.	0.02255	2.076	1.130
	0.0425	0.0663	68.95				
20.0	0.0416	0.0654	68.9	68.8 Do.	0.01725	2.988	1.159
	0.0418	0.066	68.7				

TABLE XI.

Influence of mannitol.

Conditions same as in Table VIII.

Amount of mannitol in 100 c.c. soln.	Ni deposit.	Cu deposit (conglomerate).	Cathode efficiency.	Remarks.	Sp. condy. (mhos).	Relative viscosity.	Relative density.
0.0 g.	0.0572 g.	0.0932 g.	66.08%	Bright & coarse deposit.	0.0348	1.344	1.101
1.0	0.0415	0.0678	66.25	66.2 Do.	0.03389	1.377	1.105
	0.0414	0.0678	66.15				
2.5	0.0461	0.0744	67.2	67.4 Very bright and fine grained deposit.	0.03215	1.451	1.110
	0.0506	0.0812	67.5				
5.0	0.0488	0.0782	67.6	67.5 Do.	0.03150	1.618	1.119
	0.0395	0.0650	67.4				
10.0	0.0422	0.0682	67.0	67.0 Do.	0.02660	1.839	1.134
	0.0423	0.0684	67.05				
15.0	0.0390	0.070	60.3	60.4 Dull, black and coarse deposit.	0.0234	2.195	1.148
	0.0392	0.0704	60.5				

TABLE XII.

Influence of sucrose.

Conditions same as in Table VIII.

Amount of sucrose deposit. in 100 c.c.	Ni	Cu deposit (coulometer).	Cathode efficiency.	Remarks.	Sp. condv. (mhos).	Relative viscosity.	Relative density.
0.0 g.	0.0572 g.	0.0932 g.	66.08 %	Bright & coarse deposit.	0.0348	1.344	1.101
1.0	0.0434	0.0698	67.1	} 67.2 Do.	0.03370	1.391	1.1055
	0.0444	0.0714	67.3				
2.5	0.0426	0.0686	67.23	} 67.2 Fine grained deposit	0.03287	1.462	1.111
	0.0422	0.0680	67.21				
5.0	0.0372	0.0606	66.45	} 66.4 Do.	0.03135	1.670	1.1195
	0.0376	0.0612	66.25				
10.0	0.0420	0.0690	65.9	} 65.9 Coarse and granular deposit.	0.02614	1.888	1.138
	0.0286	0.0470	65.9				

DISCUSSION.

The foregoing results show that the quality and quantity of an electrodeposit is dependent upon a large number of physical factors. These are discussed conveniently in respect of the cathode efficiency for the relevant ion, *viz.*, nickel; this is 100% under ideal conditions. Any discrepancy in this may be ascribed to the possible disturbing factors: (i) incomplete adherence of the deposit, (ii) occurrence of side reactions, *i.e.*, other than the main one for which the cathode efficiency is calculated, or (iii) solvational effects leading partly to the formation of molecular or ionic complexes in the conducting mixtures.

Electrodeposition of a metal, according to Smee, is a crystallisation process, which consists of two steps, *viz.*, (1) the formation of crystal nuclei and (2) further development of these into larger crystals. Each of these has its own velocity and the relation between these velocities determines the character of the deposit. If the velocity of (1) is greater than that of (2), a fine-grained deposit is obtained, whereas in the reverse case the deposit is coarser and the crystals big. The relation between the velocities of (1) and (2) depends, besides the factors mentioned in Table I, *i.e.*, (a) to (d), upon

(e) temperature, (f) agitation, (g) addition of foreign agents and (h) of non-electrolytes, (i) nature and structure of the base metal, (j) nature of the solvent, (k) nature of the metal deposited and (l) its valency.

The results in Table IA show that bright, lustrous and adherent deposits are obtained from $M/2$ solution at the C.D. employed; stronger and dilute solutions are found to give less satisfactory results. The favourable condition for producing metallic deposits would be the presence of a large number of metallic ions. Under such conditions each crystal would be surrounded by a large number of metallic ions, so that by the passage of the current it could grow rapidly. But if fine-grained deposits are desired it is essential to select conditions which will be unfavourable to the growth of a few crystals and will thereby foster the production of a large number of smaller crystals. The condition is fulfilled, by using $M/2$ solution, when there are not at any given time many metal ions in the solution. From our

FIG. 1

data shown in Table II (curve 1 in Fig. 1) it is seen that with the increase in concentration, $M/16$ to M , the cathode efficiency steadily increases due to increasing metal content of the bath, under the operating conditions, and corresponding diminution in hydrogen evolution at the cathode. The results in Table I_B show that with the increase in C.D. the deposit becomes finer, brighter and adherent up to a particular limit (15-40 amp./sq. ft.) after which it shows a distinct 'burning' or 'tree'-forming tendency, especially on edges and corners where the C.D. is usually much higher than the average. Loose, powdery or burnt deposits produced, especially when the C.D. is quite excessive, may be attributed to the formation and subsequent inclusion in the cathode deposits, of some basic material, such as the hydroxide or a basic salt of the metal, due to increased pH (or alkalinity) of the cathode film, caused by the local impoverishment of the metal or metal ion content round the cathode due to rapid depletion of the metal during the electrolysis. At very low C.D. (5 amp./sq. ft.), it is interesting to note that there was hardly any deposit of nickel, presumably due to the whole of the current being practically utilised in discharging hydrogen, which is further facilitated by too low a value of its over-voltage on iron (or nickel) as the cathode surface. It is also known that cathodic deposition of metals usually commences at their reversible potential and that at very small C.D. the discharge of positive ions may be regarded as a reversible process. At increasing C.D. the cathode potential becomes more negative partly as a result of concentration polarisation and partly on account of the slowness of one or other of the stages which must be involved between the initial discharge of the ion and the final orientation of the atom in the space lattice of the metal crystal. Volmer (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1928, 139, 597; 1931, 167, 165) has put forward a view that when a metal ion reaches the cathode, it is not discharged immediately but remains there on the surface between hydrated ion in the solution and that of the atom in the final state in the crystal. As a result of lateral movement over the surface the ion reaches a suitable point in the lattice where it is instantaneously discharged. From the study of the current-potential curves, obtained during the deposition of a number of metals, the conclusion has been reached that the actual neutralisation of ions occurs rapidly and that the observed polarisation is determined by the rate of formation of crystallisation nuclei by spreading across the electrode surface. If the cathode is of the same material as the metal being deposited, the points at which the ions on the surface are able to participate in the free electrons are reached without great difficulty and polarisation is not considerable. When the cathode is different from the metal being deposited, the deposition may be initially in

excess of that required when it is covered with the deposit, since there is no crystal lattice in which the ion can be discharged immediately. The anions present in the solution may possibly prevent access of the ions to the points in the lattice at which they can be discharged. This is in agreement with Barchmann's view (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1933, 39, 341).

The results reported in Table III (curve 2 in Fig. 1) show that at constant values for concentration and temperature, the current density exerts a pronouncedly marked influence on the cathode efficiency of nickel deposition, which varies within wide limits from zero to nearly cent per cent. Practically zero or very low efficiency at low C.D. is ascribable to the whole or appreciable part of the current being utilised in discharging hydrogen at the cathode as discussed previously. With the increase in C.D. this evolution is appreciably or even completely inhibited due to corresponding increase in hydrogen overvoltage; with further increase in C.D. the efficiency diminishes obviously due to hydrogen evolution, caused by a rapid depletion of the metal in the cathode film during electrolysis.

From the results in Table Ic it is seen that 30 minutes' time is the minimum duration of electrolysis necessary for a good and satisfactory deposition of nickel; the quantity improves in brightness and lustre up to 2 hours' duration. Too long a prolongation of electrolysis, however, leads to a decrease in the adhesiveness of the deposit, showing a tendency to 'peel' off, due to the impoverishment of the metal content round the cathode, especially in still solutions. With the decrease of inter-electrode distance the quality of the deposit improved (*cf.* Table Id).

From the study of the data shown in Tables IV A, B, C, it is seen that at any constant C.D. the quality and quantity (*cf.* curves 3, 3' and 3'' in Fig. 1) of the deposit improve by increasing the temperature up to a certain extent (about 50°) and deteriorate at higher temperatures (85°). The effect of rise in temperature in raising the efficiency at any C.D. is more marked at low than at high C.D. This can be explained by the fact that with the rise in temperature the conductivity increases due to increased mobilities of the ions with a concomitant increment in the cathode efficiency. Increase of temperature has two opposing effects; in the first place it favours the diffusion and tends to produce uniform and fine-grained deposit but on the other hand it decreases the velocity of crystal growth and thus fosters the formation of coarse deposits. At moderate temperatures the influence of the first factor is generally predominating but at higher temperature the second is increasingly operative. Slight diminution in efficiency observed at higher temperature (85°), especially at a high C.D. (25 amp /sq. ft.), might be due to hydrogen evolution caused by lowering

of its overvoltage at high temperature. The cathodic deposition of nickel, which is usually an irreversible process, especially at lower temperatures, tends to become, as the temperature rises, a reversible one. This may also account for the increased efficiency at high temperatures.

The results in Table V show that agitation caused by bubbling air under pressure through the electrolyte during the electrolysis gives quite smooth, regular, coherent and uniform deposits. The favourable effects of agitation at a given concentration are more marked at high than at low C.D. Similarly its effects at a given C.D. are more pronounced in dilute than in the concentrated solution. Similar results in nickel deposition were obtained by Ollard (*E.P.* 251010) by passing a current of ozonised air or oxygen through the electrolytic bath.

It is to be anticipated that superimposition of A.C. on D.C. during the electrolysis might reduce both the reaction resistance and the hydrogen overvoltage; its effect on the former might bring about an increase in current efficiency while its action on the latter might bring about the reverse effect. Our results (*cf.* Table V) show that A.C., when superimposed, lowers the efficiency appreciably (from 66% to 21% nearly). This, under the stated conditions may possibly be due to a high value for the ratio of A.C./D.C. current density, which causes a decrease in the efficiency. Similar were the conclusions of Izgarischev and Berkmann (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1925, 31, 180) and of Kohlschutter and Schodl (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1922, 5, 593). The latter workers observed no increase in the cathode efficiency of Ni deposition with lower ratio of A.C./D.C. but decrease with a higher ratio. Goodwin and Knobel (*Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1920, 37, 617) observed rapid evolution of hydrogen due to considerable diminution in its overvoltage as a result of superimposition of A.C. with sufficiently high ratio of A.C.: D.C.

A review of the literature shows that the influence of the base metal on the structure of electrodeposits, has not been fully realised. Observations by Blum and Rawdon (*Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1923, 44, 305) indicate that in general the orientation of the crystals, at least in the first layer of the deposit, is a continuation of that in the base metal. A study has, therefore, been made of the influence on the cathode efficiency and physical nature of Ni deposit of the following metals used as cathodes, *viz.*, Fe, Cu (smooth), Cu (plated), Pb, Sn, Pt (smooth), Cd (plated), Ni (plated), Co (plated), Ag, Au, Cr (plated) and Hg (plated). Our results in Table VI show that good and adherent deposits were obtained on Cu, Pb, Ni, Co, Cd, or Au-cathode; amorphous and powdery deposits were obtained on Ag and Cr cathode. The deposits on Pt cathode was unsatisfactory due to *pitting* effect. The cathode efficiency under these

conditions is in the descending order : $\text{Pb} > \text{Hg} > \text{Cu (smooth)} > \text{Cu (plated)} > \text{Cr} > \text{Co} > \text{Cd} > \text{Sn} > \text{Ni} > \text{Fe} > \text{Ag} > \text{Pt}$. It is interesting to note that there exists a rough parallelism between the cathode efficiency and hydrogen overvoltage values over the above metals. Slight but gradual diminution in the cathode efficiency as we pass on from Pb to Pt can, on the basis of hydrogen overvoltage, be attributed to gradually increasing hydrogen evolution.

No precise information is, however, available in the literature for the correlation of the cathode efficiency with the proportion of an addition agent in the electrolytic bath. This has been studied in greater details (*cf.* results in Table VII) in the case of various inorganic and organic agents, whose concentrations were varied, especially in a few cases, over a wide range. The magnitude of the above influence is illustrated by the fact that 0.025% of CrO_3 , for example, reduces the cathode efficiency from 66.1 to 0%. Various theories attempting to explain the influence of addition agents, which are generally organic or colloidal substances, exist in the literature. The possible rôle of colloidal addition agents, in general, has been discussed in a review by Blum (*Colloid Symposium Monograph*, 1921, 5, 300), who suggests the following factors for cases in which the addition agent has actually been found in the cathode deposits: "(1) Co-discharge of colloid particles and metal ions, (2) discharge of complex ions containing the metal and the colloid, (3) adsorption of colloid upon the face of the metal deposit, or (4) mechanical inclusion in the deposit." Blum further states in regard to these various possibilities that "it is difficult from the meagre data available to suggest the relative probabilities of these processes....." However, other workers have expressed preference for one or the other of the particular views outlined above. Thus Bancroft (*Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1913, 23, 266) tacitly assumes that adsorption accounts for the inclusion of the addition agent in the deposit; Fuseya and Murata (*ibid.*, 1926, 50, 235) postulated the existence of complex cations formed from the metal ion and addition agent and produced evidence to show that such complex ions are doubtless formed (*cf.* also Marie and Buffat, *J. chim. phys.*, 1927, 24, 470; Taft and Mesmore, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, 35, 2585). Among the causes which normally promote the production of rough and treed deposits is the presence of suspended impurities, especially, conducting particles of carbon, metal, etc., derived from the anodes. Upthegrove and Baker (*Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1928, 53, 389) in nickel deposition have noticed that such impurities lodge themselves upon the cathode and serve as nuclei for the growth of large-grained crystals or of trees. Much of the effect of addition agents in reducing roughness is that of counteracting the influence of

suspended matter. The extensive studies of Mathers and his students (*ibid.*, 1912, 21, 313; 1914, 24, 117; 1915, 27, 131) upon addition agents in lead baths emphasise the fact that to a great extent the effects of addition agents are specific. With the present knowledge it is impossible to predict the exact influence of any addition agent in any particular solution.

Our results show that the addition in traces or very little amount of certain agents, *viz.*, HgCl_2 , SnCl_2 , CrO_3 , pyridine, CS_2 and acetone gives loose, powdery, black and unsatisfactory deposits. It is of interest to note that the deposit is profoundly affected by the presence in the electrolyte of even small amounts of CrO_3 . Not only is the chromic acid detrimental to the physical nature of the deposit, but also its presence to the extent of 0.02 g. in 100 c.c. reduces the cathode efficiency to 7.9% and at higher concentrations (0.025 g.) no deposit is obtained. The big fall in efficiency cannot be explained through reduction of the chromic acid, but appears, chiefly, to be related to a preferential stimulation of the discharge of the hydrogen ions. Similar were the conclusions of Macnaughtan and Hammond (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1930, 26, 481). From our observations it is seen that in presence of CdCl_2 bright and lustrous deposits are obtained with increased efficiency; its increased concentration, however, produces dark deposits, which is in agreement with the earlier findings of Haring (*Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 107) and Vozdivishenski (*J. Appl. Chem. Russ.*, 1936, 9, 1416). Addition of H_2O_2 up to 0.1% to the bath improved considerably the brightness, lustre and structure of the deposit and raised the efficiency; *pitting* effect was less noticeable. This might be due to a considerable diminution in hydrogen evolution. Its increased concentration, however, fosters the formation of dull and dark deposits by reducing the *throwing power* of the solution. The beneficial effect of H_2O_2 seems to have been noticed earlier, especially by Hans Stager (*loc. cit.*), Kohlschutter (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1920, 3, 614) and Potter (*loc. cit.*). Addition of $\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$, $18\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1%) to the bath produces marked improvement in the lustre fineness and general character of the deposit though it causes a diminution in the cathode efficiency due to co-deposition of Al. The presence of Al in the cathode deposit was detected by the usual qualitative tests. That $\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$, $18\text{H}_2\text{O}$ functions as the most efficient addition agent in nickel deposition may possibly be attributed to its capacity to pass into a colloidal state due to hydrolysis, as evidenced by a sudden but distinct development of opalescence in the solution and its subsequent inclusion in the cathode deposit, where its presence hinders the crystal growth, thus resulting in the formation of a fine-grained deposit. The favourable effects of this addition agent, especially in the deposition of Zn from zinc

bath have been attributed to its buffer action by Thompson (*Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1926, 80, 193) who failed to detect its presence in the cathode deposit. Hard, brittle and *pitted* or *cracked* deposits obtained in the presence of very small amounts of the agents, such as, glue, thymol, egg-albumin, dextrine and gelatin (*cf.* our results) clearly indicate that a nickel depositing solution is very susceptible to the action of colloids. Phillips (*loc. cit.*) and Cuthbertson (*loc. cit.*) are of opinion that addition of organic substances are of no use to a nickel-plating bath but they make the bath complicated and hence difficult to control.

FIG. 2(a).
% by volume.

FIG. 2(b).

It is to be anticipated that the complex formation would be simpler when the addition agents were of molecular weights smaller than those characteristics of colloids. Experiments were, therefore, carried out on measurements of the cathode efficiency in the presence of varying proportion of

methyl alcohol (Table VIII and Fig. 2a), ethyl alcohol (Table IX and Fig. 2b), glycerol (Table X and Fig. 3a), mannitol (Table XI and Fig. 3b) and sucrose (Table XII). Their influence in respect of the above quantity is substantially analogous as is seen from the results. The cathode efficiency increases steadily with the progressive addition of the non-electrolyte in all cases till it approaches a limiting value; it remains practically constant being unaffected with the further addition; in the case of methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol and glycerol but diminishes in the case of mannitol and

FIG. 3(b).

sucrose. The quality of the deposit also improves with the increase in concentration of the addendum up to a particular limit but deteriorates with further addition. This may be accounted for as follows. The possible disturbing factors leading to a deficit in the deposition of a metal are: (i) the existence of the cation in two forms, (ii) the dissolution of the deposited metal by the medium due to solvent action, (iii) chemical corrosion brought about by the oxygen present, or (iv) discharge of hydrogen. The loss thus brought about is a function of C.D., temperature, electrode surface, conductivity, p_n of the solution etc., as demonstrated by the work of Foerster and Siedel (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1897, 14, 106). The addition of non-electrolyte may, however, alter the condition of the bath and bring about the diminution in the concentration of the nickel ions in the solutions thus lowering the solvent effect. It is, therefore, to be anticipated that an increase in the cathode efficiency would come about by increasing the concentration of the non-electrolyte up to a certain limiting value; our foregoing results (*cf.* curves in Figs. 2 and 3) are in agreement with this deduction. Our data with mannitol and sucrose show that the cathode efficiency after reaching the maximum values diminishes with further addition. This might be due to some interaction between the conducting material and the medium or possibly due to increased resistance of the bath solution. A number of further properties such as the conductivity, viscosity and density for the same mixtures were, therefore, studied. Schall (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1894, 14, 701) found that usually the conductivity is decreased when the water of solution is replaced in part by alcohol, which is in agreement with the foregoing results. Hantzsch (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1900, 26, 332) studied the influence of non-electrolytes on the conductivity of electrolytes. The addition of methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol and acetone to aqueous solution of alkali or alkaline earth metals diminished the conductivity slightly and approximately to the same extent. Jones and Rouiller (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1906, 36, 427) have shown that the relative migration velocities of silver nitrate are influenced largely by the nature of the solvent, probably due to the varying degrees of combination of the solvent with one of the ions.

The specific conductivity, relative viscosity and specific gravity graphs (Figs. 2-3) show a remarkable similarity; curves showed no discontinuity. It is very likely that the occurrence of maxima in the cathode efficiency-non-electrolyte concentration curves (not revealed in other curves), might be due to the discharge of complex cation containing the metal and non-electrolyte (*cf.* previous communications from these laboratories, Joshi and co-workers, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 174, 185; 1941, 18, 177).

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